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Development of high yielding with durable resistance against Mungbean yellow mosaic virus genotypes in Blackgram

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Abstract

The Blackgram culture VBG04-008 is a cross derivative of blackgram Vamban 3 x *Vigna mungo* var. *silvestris* 8 is released as TNAU blackgram VBN (Bg) 7 maturing in 65-70 days with an average height of 17 cm and suited for cultivation under both under rainfed and irrigated conditions. It has a yield potential of 981 Kg per hectare. This culture is resistant to Yellow Mosaic Virus, Powdery mildew and Leaf Curl Virus and less damage of pod borer. It possesses desirable characters like high protein content (21.05%), crude fibre (5.90g/100g) and iron (3.76 mg/100g). Grains are medium sized with black in colour. It is recommended for cultivation in Tamil Nadu, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka and Orissa.

Keywords: VBG04-008; Blackgram; VBN 7 Mung Bean Yellow Mosaic Virus; Powdery mildew-Rainfed; Irrigated

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